

Antifungal effect of silver-containing bionanomaterials based on humic ligands

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In 2022, the World Health Organization published a list of fungal priority pathogens. It included 19 fungal species, four of which are *Candida* fungi. They interested us due to their wide distribution area, high virulence, and the increase in cases of drug-resistant candidiasis. There is a need for new antifungal drugs that can fight these pathogens. Bionanomaterials made from natural humic substances and silver nanoparticles can become such. The goal of the study is to research the antifungal effect of silver-containing bionanomaterials based on humic ligands.

The study used clinical strains of *Candida* fungi, which were isolated in the bacteriological laboratory of the clinics of the Siberian State Medical University from various materials from patients: two strains of *C. albicans* from sputum, one strain of *C. albicans* from discharge from a surgical wound, one strain of *Candida* spp. from sputum and three strains of *Candida* spp. from urine. To study the potential antifungal effect, samples of silver-containing bionanomaterials based on humic ligands were taken, which were synthesized in the Laboratory of Natural Humic Systems of the Department of Chemistry, Lomonosov Moscow State University. We used two samples of bionanomaterials synthesized by thermal (CHP-AgNPs-kt) and microwave (CHP-AgNPs-mw) methods based on a common ligand – a matrix of humic acids from brown coal CHP (“Powhumus”, Humintech Ltd.), according to the method described in [1]. To clarify the role of humic substances in the antifungal effect of bionanomaterials, two samples of humic substances were studied from brown coal – CHP (“Powhumus”, Humintech Ltd.) and CHGen (Genesis LLC). We selected strains of *Candida* fungi capable of forming biofilms. Then, the studied substances were screened for antifungal properties. The effect of the samples on the formed biofilms was assessed. We also assessed the viability of fungi in biofilms after exposure to the studied substances.

Seven strains of *Candida* fungi capable of forming biofilms were selected. According to the screening results, the best was the bionanomaterial CHP-AgNPs-mw, which suppressed the growth of all the studied strains. It was able to destroy the biofilms of four of the seven studied strains (two strains of *C. albicans* from sputum, the strain of *C. albicans* from discharge from a surgical wound, one strain of *Candida* spp. from urine). At the same time, the humic substance sample CHGen also demonstrated antifungal properties, suppressing the growth of three strains out of seven (two strains of *C. albicans* from sputum, the strain of *C. albicans* from discharge from a surgical wound) and destroying the biofilm of the strain of *Candida* spp. from sputum. Evaluation of the viability of fungi in biofilms after exposure showed the destruction of the biofilm structure and the death of cells inside it.

Silver-containing bionanomaterials based on humic ligands exhibit antifungal properties and destroy formed fungal biofilms. In this regard, they are promising substances for the development of antifungal drugs.

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References.

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